

Stage 1: Initial Review (August, 2025)

Identification

Records identified from:
Lens.org (n = 90)

Screening

Review data
(n = 90)

Removed before screening:
Duplicate records (n = 2)

Title/Abstract screening
(n = 88)

Records excluded
(n = 6)

Full text screening
(n = 82)

Records excluded
(n = 8)

Included

Studies included for data extraction
(n = 74)

Stage 2: Update Review (May, 2026)

Records identified from:
Lens.org (n = 385)

Review data
(n = 385)

Removed before screening:
Duplicate records (n = 93)

Title/Abstract
screening (n = 292)

Records excluded
(n = 89)

Full text screening
(n = 203)

Records excluded
(n = 65)

Studies included for data extraction
(n = 138)